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PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF IN SITU GELLING MICONAZOLE NITRATE LIQUID VAGINAL SUPPOSITORY

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ABSTRACT

The key purpose of this study was to prepare and evaluate of in situ gelling Miconazole nitrate liquid vaginal suppository for fungal infection. *In situ* gelation is a process of gel formulation at the site of application, in which a drug product formulation that exists as a liquid has been transformed into gel upon contact with body fluid or at body temperature. To solve the problem of conventional solid suppositories it would be desirable to develop a liquid suppository which forms a gel at body temperature with suitable gel strength not to be leaked out from vagina after administration and with a suitable bioadhesive force. The liquid vaginal suppository was prepared by cold method using as Poloxamer 407 & 188 as thermo reversible polymer and HPMC, Carbopol 934 and Sodium alginate as mucoadhesive polymer. Liquid suppository was prepared by different combinations of drug and excipients. Formulation was evaluated in terms of pH, Gelation temperature, Gel strength, Mucoadhesive property, Drug content estimation and *in vitro* drug release etc. Results indicated that HPMC based liquid suppository gave better gelation temperature than others and it was observed that the increased in concentration of HPMC shows decreased in gel strength, mucoadhesive property and drug release of formulation.

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INTRODUCTION

Suppository are medicated solid dosage forms generally intended for used in rectum, vagina and to a lesser extent, the urethra. Suppositories can be used for two main purposes: (a) to act locally as a protective around the tissue where it is inserted (b) to act simply as a vehicle or carrier of an active drug that we want to be absorbed at the site of insertion but distributed systemically to produce an effect throughout the entire body. The vagina has been favourable site for both local as well as systemic delivery of drug for female associated condition due to the presence of rich blood supply, good (high) permeability and large surface area. Vaginal route of administration is especially useful for those patients who have difficulty in swallowing oral medicines. Vaginal formulation have various advantages like improved enzymatic drug stability, avoidance of overdosing, avoid gut and hepatic first pass metabolism & side effects, easy to formulate and self medication. Conventional vaginal drug delivery systems have some limitations like irritation and itching of vagina, low residence time and messy to apply it overcome by liquid vaginal suppository having significance like easy to administer, long retention time, forms a gel at body temperature, has a suitable gel strength, suitable mucoadhesive force and proper spreading on vaginal surface (epithelium). Drugs are introduced into vagina either as solid or liquid form for local and systemic action. Miconazole nitrate is an antifungal agent and also limited antibacterial properties. Azoles inhibit biosynthesis of ergosterol or sterols, destructive the fungal cell membrane and also change the permeability of membrane. It can be used against species of *leishmania protozoa* which are a type of unicellular parasite that also contain ergosterol in their cell membranes. Due to various advantageous effect of Miconazole nitrate, it was incorporated in to liquid vaginal suppository as an antifungal drug against vaginal infection like Candida infection (*Candida albicans*). Poloxamer are thermo reversible polymer and base of liquid vaginal suppository whereas Carbopol, HPMC and sodium alginate are mucoadhesive polymer. In present study poloxamer 188 and poloxamer 407 are selected to formulate a liquid suppository because they both have known to be low toxicity, less skin irritation, excellent water solubility and high solubilizing capacity for drugs, good drug release characteristics and compatibility with other excipients and in addition to poloxamer 407 and 188 are solutions at low temperature, but will gel at higher temperature. Poloxamer liquid suppositories containing sodium alginate appears to be a preferred formulation for drugs that are sensitive to extensive first – pass metabolism.^[1-13]

Sodium alginate contains carboxyl group and hydroxyl group, which form strong bond between mucosal membrane and retard the release. HPMC contains the hydroxyl group so they can use as mucoadhesive agent, which can bind to vaginal mucosal lining and bind oligosaccharide chains. Carbopol 934 contains carboxyl group so they can use as a mucoadhesive agent, which can bind to the vaginal mucous lining and bind to oligosaccharide chains. They have less skin irritation than others.

In this study we developed thermo sensitive as well as mucoadhesive liquid vaginal suppository containing Miconazole nitrate using poloxamer (188 and 407) and mucoadhesive (HPMC, Carbopol and sodium alginate) polymer. The physiochemical properties such as bioadhesive or mucoadhesive force, gelation temperature and gel strength of various formulations of Miconazole nitrate, poloxamer and mucoadhesive polymers were evaluated. Also, the antifungal effect of Miconazole nitrate was studied.^[14-17]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material

Miconazole nitrate (Lyra pharmaceuticals, Baddi). Poloxamer 188 and 407 (Yarrow chemical products Mumbai), Carbopol, HPMC, Sodium alginate, Disodium Hydrogen phosphate and Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (Loba chem. Ltd, Mumbai), Methanol and Ethanol (S.D. Fine chem. Ltd, Mumbai), Sabouraud Media (Hi media).

Methods

Preliminary studies:-

Preliminary studies were conducted to properly develop cold method for production of liquid suppository. Liquid suppositories were prepared in several batches by varying the poloxamer (P) ratio and amount of poloxamer 188 and poloxamer 407 are carried in order to find out the influence of amount of poloxamer on gelation temperature of liquid suppository. The temperature should be remaining in the range up to 30 – 36⁰ C.

Preparations of Miconazole nitrate liquid vaginal suppository:-

Miconazole nitrate Liquid vaginal different formulations were prepared by using different concentration of poloxamer (188 and 407) and mucoadhesive polymer (HPMC, sodium alginate, Carbopol) according to procedures described by *Choi et al.*, The liquid suppository was prepared by cold method. 0.2 g Miconazole nitrate with or without a mucoadhesive polymer was dissolved in distilled water by agitation at room temperature. After cooling the solution to 4⁰C, poloxamer 407 and poloxamer 188 were slowly added, with agitation. The mixture was then kept overnight at 4⁰C until a viscous and clear transparent solution was obtained. Composition of in situ gelling liquid suppositories of Miconazole nitrate is given in table no.1

Table no.1: Composition of in situ gelling liquid suppositories of Miconazole nitrate.

Composition g/10ml	F0	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Miconazole nitrate	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Poloxamer 407	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4
Poloxamer 188	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
HPMC	-	0.02	0.04	0.06	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sodium alginate	-	-	-	-	0.02	0.04	0.06	-	-	-
Carbopol 934	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.02	0.04	0.06
Distilled water	q.s to 10 ml									

EVALUATION OF LIQUID VAGINAL SUPPOSITORIES:

pH

The pH values of liquid suppository formulation were determined by using calibrated pH meter (Control dynamic pH meter).

Measurement of gelation temperature

Gelation temperature was assessed using the tube tilting method. 2 ml of gel was transferred to test tubes immersed in a water bath at 4 °C and sealed with aluminium foil. The temperature of water bath was increased in increments of 1 °C and left to balance for 5 min at each new setting. The samples were examined for gelation^[18-25]

Gel strength

Liquid suppository weighing 50 g was put into 100 ml graduated cylinder and gelation was accomplished using thermostat at 36.5 °C. The apparatus used for measuring the gel strength weighed 35 g and was placed onto top of liquid suppository. The gel strength which considered as viscosity of the liquid suppository at physiological temperature was determined by the time in seconds the apparatus took to sink 5 cm down through the liquid suppository.^[26-30]

Figure 1: Gel strength measuring instrument (a) weight, (b) device, (c) measuring cylinder, (d) Liquid.

Mucoadhesive force

A section of tissue was cut from fundus of rat rectum and secured with mucosal side out onto each glass vial using a rubber band and aluminium cap. The vials with rectal tissues were stored at 36.5 °C for 10 min. One vial with a tissue was connected to a balance and other vial was placed on a height adjustable pan. Liquid suppository was added onto the rectal tissue on the other vials. Then, the height of vials was adjusted so the liquid suppository could be placed between the mucosal tissues of both vials. The weight was increased until two vials were detached. Bioadhesive force, the detached stress (dyne/cm²), was determined from minimal weights that detached the two vials. Following formula was used to determine mucoadhesive force in (dyne/cm² * 10²),

$$\text{Detached stress (dyne/cm}^2\text{)} = (m) \times (g/A)$$

Where,

m = weight required for detached of two membrane in gram

g = Acceleration due to gravity [980 cm/s²]

A = Area of tissue exposed^[31-33]

Drug content estimation

Five ml of the solution was pipette and dissolved in about 70 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) in a 100 ml volumetric flask. The flask was shaken for 10 min and volume made up to the 100 ml mark. After shaking for 2 min, the solution was filtered; rejecting first few ml of filtrate. From the above solution, 1 ml was transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with phosphate buffer. The absorbance of this solution was recorded at against blank reagent using UV spectrophotometer. Drug content studies were carried out in triplicate for each formulation batch. The concentration of the drug present in formulation was computed from the equation obtained from calibration curve.

In vitro release studies:-

This study was carried out by using apparatus i.e. Keshary-Chein diffusion cell. Nine formulations were evaluated for *in vitro* release using Keshary-Chein diffusion cell. The 1 ml of suppository was put on the cellophane membrane (0.45 μm , Millipore) and then the membrane wax affixed in the diffusion cell. After the interval of 1 h the 1 ml of sample was withdrawn from diffusion cell and the cell was again replenished with 1 ml fresh phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) 1ml. The sample was diluted 10 times and was analyzed on UV spectrophotometer. To evaluate the mechanism of drug from liquid vaginal suppository formulation, the release data were fitted according to different kinetic equations like Zero order, first order and Higuchi square root equations.

Antifungal studies

The prepared formulation was tested by cup plate method. This method is based upon the diffusion of an antifungal from a cavity through the solidified agar layer of a petri plate used for study. Growth of inoculated microorganism is inhibited entirely in a circular area 'zone' around a cavity containing a solution of the antifungal. Weighed 16.25 g of Sabouraud dextrose agar was transferred in a 500 ml of conical flask and 250 ml of purified water and some amount of heat is applied to dissolve it completely. This mixture was sterilized for 15 min at 121° C at 15 lb pressure in autoclave for about 20 min. and then cooled it at room temperature and the fungal strain (*Candida albicans*) was dispersed in the medium and then the medium was poured it into the petri dish and allowed it to cool it for sometime at room temperature until it forms solidifies at room temperature and then the t cups are bored in petri dish with the help of sterile steel bore of 6mm and calculated concentration of the liquid suppository formulation (F2) were placed in the bores and incubated the petri plate for 72 h at 37° c on incubators. Then the zone of inhibitions was observed and calculated the radius of the zone of inhibition.^[34-36]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary study

Gelation temperature of poloxamer solutions: Gelation temperature is the temperature at which the liquid phase makes a transition to gel. A gelation temperature of liquid suppository would be 30 – 36 °C. The gelation temperature of liquid suppository is lower than 30 °C, gelation occurring at room temperature leading to difficulty in manufacturing, handling and administering. If the gelation temperature is higher than 36 °C, the suppository still stays as a liquid at body temperature, resulting leakage from vagina. Therefore, liquid suppository must have the suitable gelation temperature and to form a gel phase instantly in the vagina. Various mixture of poloxamer P407 and P188 gelled at the suitable gelation temperature while solution of each poloxamer alone did not gel at the desirable range in table 2. The gelation temperature of 10% and 20% of P407 or 5% and 10% of P188 was greater than 55°C. The increment in poloxamer 188 concentration led to an apparent dramatic increase of micellar size and polydispersibility which could be reason for such reduction in gelation temperature. This indicates that P407 or P188 alone could not provide the suitable gelation temperature. So we tried to formulate mixtures of P407 and P188. As the concentration of P407 increased, the mixtures needed smaller amounts of P188 to gel at desirable gelation temperature. This during preliminary studies formulation containing P407/P188 in ratio of 22/5 % w/w was selected as an optimized formulation for further study it showed gelation temperature in range 30-36 °C.

Table 2:-Gelation temperature of poloxamer solution.

Poloxamer	Concentration (%)	Gelation temperature (°C)
Poloxamer 407	10	>50
	12	>50
	15	Slightly viscous at 47
	18	Gelation at 26-27
	24	Gelation at 22-23
Poloxamer 188	5	>50
	10	>50
	15	48-50
	20	45-47
P407/P188	15/5	>50
	15/10	>50
	15/15	>50
	15/20	Slightly viscous at 50
	18/5	>50
	18/10	>50
	18/15	Slightly viscous at 47-50
	18/20	Slightly viscous at 42
24/5	Gelation at 30-33	

pH

The maximum pH of all formulations was found to be 7.89 and the minimum pH was 7.28 (Table3). The results showed that all the formulations had pH values close to vaginal (7.1-7.4) pH range.

Gelation temperature

The effect of bioadhesive polymer on gelation temperature was studied. HPMC, Sodium alginate and Carbopol 934 were selected as bioadhesive polymers. The gelation temperature lowering effect of mucoadhesive/bioadhesive polymer was explained by the ability to bind to the polyoxyethylene chains present in poloxamer molecules through hydrogen bonding. They were promoting dehydration, causing an increase in entanglement of adjacent molecules and extensively increasing intermolecular hydrogen bonding which was leading gelation lowering temperature. The sodium alginate showed the stronger intermolecular hydrogen bonding than Carbopol 934 and HPMC, so it showed gelation at lower temperature than others. The mean average decreasing order in the gelation temperature noticed with all the formulations with different concentration of polymers (0.2%, 0.4%, and 0.6%) was found to be as: Sodium alginate<Carbopol<HPMC(Figure 2).

Figure 2: Gelation temperature of different mucoadhesive polymer.

Gel strength

When liquid suppository is prepared, gel strength is important characteristic of dosage form because it allows the easy insertion of suppository and no leak from vagina. The increase in gel strength caused by the addition of mucoadhesive/bioadhesive polymer such as HPMC, sodium alginate and Carbopol might be attributed to that, the polymer with hydrophilic groups as the carboxyl and hydroxyl groups can be bind strongly to the oligosaccharide chains by forming hydrogen bonds, electrostatic attraction or hydrophobic interaction. At the high gel strength, it is difficult to insert the suppository and if the lower gel strength then suppository would leak from vagina. It is reported that the optimal *in situ* gelling and mucoadhesive liquid suppositories must have gel strength, in the range of 10-15 seconds. The mean average decreasing order in the gel strength noticed with all the formulation at different concentration of polymers (0.2%, 0.4%, and 0.6%) was found to be as: Sodium alginate>Carbopol>HPMC(Figure3).

Figure 3: Gel strength of different mucoadhesive polymer.

Mucoadhesive force

The addition of different mucoadhesive polymer reinforced the mucoadhesive force of vaginal gel and mucoadhesive force appreciably increased as the concentration of mucoadhesive polymer increased from 0.2, 0.4 and 0.6%. The mucoadhesive force arranged according to their mucoadhesive forces enhancing effect at different concentration of polymers (0.2%, 0.4%, and 0.6%) of vaginal liquid suppository: Sodium alginate>Carbopol>HPMC (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Mucoadhesive force of different mucoadhesive polymer.

Drug content

The drug content was calculated for all formulations, the result was shown in Table 3. For the various formulation drug content varied from 83.32 to 96.62%. The formulation containing no mucoadhesive polymer then drug content was found to be 94.35% and formulations (F1-F3) containing different concentration of HPMC (0.25%, 0.4%, 0.6%) then drug content was found to be 89.93%, 90.76%, 91.16% and formulations (F4-F6) containing different concentration of sodium alginate (0.25%, 0.4%, 0.6%) then drug content was found to be 91.37%, 92.50%, 92.81% and formulations (F7-F9) containing different concentration of sodium alginate (0.25%, 0.4%, 0.6%) then drug content was found to be 88.05%, 88.65%, 89.14% respectively.

Table 3: Physiological Evaluation Data of liquid vaginal suppository of Miconazole nitrate.

Formulations	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
pH	7.42	7.42	7.58	7.28	7.48	7.70	7.60	7.89	7.70
Gelation Temperature (°C)	35	34	30	33	31	30	34	33	31
Gel strength (sec) ± SD	21.1± 0.2	25.2± 0.3	30.1± 0.1	34.2± 0.2	38.1± 0.1	46.1± 0.1	26.2± 0.2	29.1± 0.2	33.2± 0.2
Mucoadhesive force (dyne/cm ² *10 ²)± SD	68.9± 0.4	77.2± 0.2	141.1 ± 0.4	98.7± 0.4	150.4 ±0.3	169.5 ±0.4	89.2± 0.1	120.4 ± 0.3	150.7 ± 0.3
Drug content (%) ± SD	89.93 ±0.04	90.7± 0.03	91.69 ±0.2	91.37 ±0.2	92.50 ±0.08	92.81 ±0.02	88.05 ±0.03	88.65 ±0.03	89.14 ±0.02
Release of drug in 8h (%) ± SD	88.26 ±0.3	87.05 ±0.04	84.64 ±0.2	86.87 ±0.10	83.32 ±0.2	75.27 ±0.05	71.17 ±0.03	68.81 ±0.08	44.54 ±0.03

*Values represent the mean ±SD (n=3)

In-vitro release of Miconazole nitrate from liquid vaginal suppositories

The effect of bioadhesive or mucoadhesive polymer on the release of Miconazole nitrate from liquid vaginal suppositories was shown in table 3. In the present study it was found that the formulation F0 containing no bioadhesive or mucoadhesive polymer so it released near about 98.11% of the drug in 6 h. The addition of bioadhesive or mucoadhesive polymers slows down the drug release from all formulations because of with an increase in viscosity of the formulation which allowed less penetration of dissolution fluid into the gel. It was observed that formulation containing HPMC showed comparatively fast release than other polymer. It was due to low viscosity which allowed more rapid penetration of dissolution fluid into gel. The release retarding effect of different polymers was as follow: Carbopol 934>sodium alginate>HPMC.

Figure 5: *In vitro* zero order drug release profile of formulation F1-F3.

Figure 6: *In vitro* zero order drug release profile of formulation F4-F6.

Figure 7: *In vitro* zero order drug release profile of formulation F7-F9.

Analysis of drug release rate

It is clear from the table that the release of drug from formulation is not followed zero order and it indicates that the dissolution rate of the drug is independent upon the amount of the drug available for diffusion and dissolution from the matrix. The dissolution data of all formulations when fitted in accordance with the first order equation it is clear that a linear relationship was obtained with 'R' (Correlation coefficient) value near about to unity and higher than 'R' obtained from the zero order equations of all formulations. In this research, all the formulation could be best expressed by Higuchi's classical diffusion equation, as the plots showed high linearity 'R' = 0.930 to 0.995.

Formulations	Zero order release (R^2)	First order release (R^2)	Higuchi release (R^2)
F1	0.897	0.990	0.995
F2	0.914	0.993	0.998
F3	0.935	0.976	0.995
F4	0.871	0.929	0.986
F5	0.961	0.887	0.949
F6	0.991	0.936	0.930
F7	0.922	0.99	0.996
F8	0.981	0.987	0.964
F9	0.953	0.988	0.985

Antifungal studies

In this study the inhibition zone of marketed formulation like Miconazole 1 was compared with formulation F2. Then the zone of inhibitions of both formulations was examined and calculated the radius of the zone of inhibition. The zone of inhibition around the cavity was observed. The diameter was measured.

Table 6.1 Inhibition zone of prepared liquid suppository formulation.

Formulation	Inhibition Zone (mm)
Miconazole 1	53.49±0.46
F2	50.22±0.12

CONCLUSION

Poloxamer composition plays the most significant role in the formulation as it directly affects the gelation temperature of formulation which is the most important parameter. All nine formulations were evaluated for pH, gelation temperature, gel strength, mucoadhesive, release rate etc. On the basis of evaluation data F2 formulation containing P407/P188/HPMC (2.4/0.5/0.04%w/v) showed the most promising results. The liquid vaginal suppository of Miconazole nitrate for fungal infection was found to be a better option in the treatment by providing sustained release of action and this dosage form has lot of potential for further research work and *in-vivo* study.

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REFERENCES

1. Coben LJ, Libermann HA. In: Lachman L, Libermann HA and Kanig JL, editors. 'Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy' special Indian edition 2009, CBS publisher; page no.567-588.
2. Bradshaw, Ann. Rectal suppository insertion: the reliability of the evidence as a basis for nursing practice. *Journal of Clinical Nursing* 2006;16 (1): 98-103
3. Abd-El-Maeboud KH, T El-Naggar, EMM El-Hawi, SAR Mahmoud, S Abd-El-Hay. Rectal suppository: commonsense and mode of insertion. *The Lancet. Elsevier Science* 1991;338 (8770):798-800.
4. Tahibah university. suppositories. department of pharmacy. In. *pharmaceutice IV (PHR308)*; college of health science 2009-2010.
5. Troy David B, Beringer Paul. Remington: *The Science and Practice of Pharmacy*. 21th ed., Lippincott Williams & Wilkins 2006; 883-885.
6. Taksande jayshree B, Bhojar Vyankatesh S, Trivedi Rashmi V and Umekar Milind J. Development and Evaluation In- situ Gel Formulation of Clindamycin HCL Vaginal Application. *Der Pharmacia Lettre* 2013;5(2):364-369.
7. V Ashok, Kumar R Manoj, Murali D and Chaterjee Arkendu. A Review of vaginal route as a systemic drug delivery. *Earth journal* 2012; 1:1-19.
8. Tarakaramo Ch, Reddy K srinivasa. Emerging and Application of Vaginal Drug Delivery: An review. *IJCST* 2014;4(40):369_373.
9. Patel Anita, Patel Jayvadan. Vagina as a application site for drug delivery. *IJNDD* 2012;4(1):17-23.
10. Khan Arshad Bashir, Saha Chanky. A Review on Vaginal drug delivery system. *RJ Pharm sci* 2014;4(4):142-147.
11. Keshwani Bhawana, Sharma Divyanshu, Arora Pankaj, Chatterjee Arindam. Novel concepts in vaginal drug delivery. *J Pharm Res* 2014;3(10):184-187.
12. Sahoo chinmaya Keshari, Nayak Prakash kumar, Sarangi Deepak Kumar, Sahoo Tanmaya Keshari. Intra vaginal drug delivery system: an overview. *AJADD* 2013;1(1):43-55.
13. Dobaria N, Mashru R and Vadia NH. Vaginal drug delivery systems: a review of current status. *East and Central African Journal of Pharmaceutical Science* 2007;10:3-13.
14. Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ. *Hand book of pharmaceutical Excipients*. 6th ed. Pharmaceutical Press London: 2006:506-509
15. Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ. *Hand book of pharmaceutical Excipients*. 6th ed. Pharmaceutical Press London: 2006:326-327.
16. Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ. *Hand book of pharmaceutical Excipients*. 6th ed. Pharmaceutical Press London: 2006:622-624.
17. Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ. *Hand book of pharmaceutical Excipients*. 6th ed. Pharmaceutical Press London: 2006.110-114.

18. Jaafar Iman S, Radhi Ameera A. Formulation and In vitro Evaluation of In situ Gelling Liquid Suppository of Promethazine HCl. WJPR 2015; 1(11):273-286.
19. Hani Umme, Shivkumar HG. Development of Miconazole nitrate thermosensitive bioadhesive vaginal gel for vaginal candidiasis. AJADD 2013;1(3): 358-368.
20. Ramandan Afaf A. Formulation and evaluation of bioadhesive vaginal suppositories containing Miconazole nitrate. Int J Pharm Bio Sci 2013;4(1):455-472.
21. Yenkar P, Mayee Rahul, Nawale R, Chavan R, Salunke T and Bhojar V. Bio responsive insitu gel of Clindamycin for Vaginal application. RRJPPS 2013;2(2):26-32.
22. Youg Chul Soon, Oh Yu-Kyoung, Jung Se Hyun, Rhee jong-dal, Kim Chong-kook. Preparation of Ibuprofen loaded liquid suppository using eutectic mixture system with menthol. European Journal of Pharmaceutics Sciences 2004;23: 347-353.
23. El-Enin Amal SM Abu and El-Feky Gina S. Formulation and Evaluation of in situ gelling Tenoxicam Liquid suppositories. JLM.2013;1:23-32.
24. Karanvana Sinem Yaprak, Rencher Seda, Senyigit Zeynep Ay and Baloglu Esra. A new in situ formulation of Itraconazole for vaginal administration. Pharmacy and Pharmacology. 2013;3:417-426.
25. Pasztor E, Mako A, Csoka G, fenyvesi Zs, Benko R, Prosszer M, Marton S, Antal I, Klebovich I. New formulation of in situ gelling Metolose based liquid suppository. Drug Development and Industrial Pharmacy 2011;3(1):1-7.
26. Haidy Abass, Rabab Kamel, Abdelbary Ahmed. Metronidazole bioadhesive vaginal suppositories: Formulation, in vitro and in vivo evaluation. Int. J Pharm Sci. 2012 2;4(1):344-353.
27. Keny RV, Lourenco CF. Formulation and evaluation of thermoreversible in situ gelling and mucoadhesive Dilitiazem Hydrochloride liquid suppository. International Journal of Pharma and Bio sciences 2010;1(1):1-17.
28. Jadhav UG, Dias RJ, Mali KK, Havaldar VD. Development of in situ gelling and mucoadhesive liquid suppository of Ondansetron. International Journal of Chem Tech Research 2009;1(4):953-961.
29. Barakat Nahal S. In vitro and In vivo characteristics of thermo gelling rectal delivery system of Etodolac. APPS Pharma Sci Tech. 2009;1(3):724-731.
30. Al-Wiswasi Noor N and Al-Khedairy Eman BH. Formulation and in vitro Evaluation of in situ gelling liquid suppositories of Naproxen. Iraqi J. Pharm.Sci. 2008;17(1):31-38.
31. Youg Chul Soon, Oh Yu-Kyoung, Jung Se Hyun, Rhee jong-dal, Kim Chong-kook. Preparation of Ibuprofen loaded liquid suppository using eutectic mixture system with menthol. European Journal of Pharmaceutics Sciences 2004;23: 347-353.
32. Yun Mi-ok, Choi Han-Gon, Jung Jae-Hee, Kim Chong-Kook. Development of thermo reversible insulin liquid suppository with bioavailability enhancement. International Journal of Pharmaceutics 1999: 137-145.
33. Ryu Jei-Man, Chung Suk-Jae and Shim Chang-Koo. Increased bioavailability of Propranolol in rats by retaining thermally gelling liquid suppositories in rectum. journal of controlled release 1998:163-172.
34. K czaczyk, K Trajanowska, B Stachowiak. Inhibition of Ergosterol Biosynthesis in fungal plant pathogen by bacillus species. Polish J of Environment studies 2002;11(5):593-597.
35. Ignacio Ciara, Thai Dorothy. Comparative analysis of antifungal activity of natural remedies vs Miconazole nitrate salt against Candida albicans. Biological sciences department 2005:1-25.
36. Nagalakshmi S, Ramaswamy Radhika, Renuga, Sowjanya, Premalatha, Vijayanjani and Shanmuganathan S. Design, development and evaluation of Miconazole nitrate topical gel for fungal infection. IJPSR 2015;6(3)1266-1272.

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